

Studies in the Synthesis of Quinoline Derivatives: Part VI¹. Synthesis of Pyranoquinolines and Quinolinolactones

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Received August 11, 1971

5-Methyl- and 5,7-dimethyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3, 2-c) quinoline and their 3-phenyl derivatives were prepared from 2-methyl- and 2, 8-dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline respectively by Perkin reaction. Several substituted acetoacetaryl amides were condensed with ethyl bromoacetate to give α -carboethoxymethylacetoacetaryl amides and cyclised with conc. sulphuric acid to 4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-acetic acid derivatives. These on treatment with acetic anhydride gave quinoline-lactone derivatives. Similar condensation on ethyl bromo propionate gave 4-methyl-, 4, 6-dimethyl- and 4, 8-dimethyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-propionic acid derivatives.

Brown *et al.*² carried out Pechmann reaction on 2,4-dihydroxyquinoline with malic acid in the presence of conc. sulphuric acid and obtained 5-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3,2-c)

quinoline. Studies in the synthesis of pyrano (3,2-c)quinoline derivatives being meagre, it was thought of interest to build up α -pyrone ring on 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives by application of Perkin reaction. When 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline was subjected to Perkin reaction with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, no pure product could be isolated. On replacement of sodium acetate by triethylamine reaction proceeded smoothly and the product obtained was assigned 5-methyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano (3,2-c)quinoline (1) structure on the basis of analytical results. Its IR spectrum (Nujol) showed a characteristic lactonyl carbonyl band at 1725 cm^{-1} .

Again 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline on treatment with acetic anhydride, phenylacetic acid and triethylamine gave 5-methyl-3-phenyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano(3,2-c)quinoline.

Similarly 5,7-dimethyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano(3,2-c)quinoline and its 3-phenyl derivative were prepared from 2,8-dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline.

Naturally occurring furoquinoline alkaloids are furo(2,3-b)quinoline derivatives with unsubstituted furan ring. An attempt to prepare such furoquinolines met with failure as ozonolysis³ of α -allylacetoacetanilide did not succeed. An attempt was made to synthesise furo(2,3-b) quinoline (II) derivative by first reducing the ester of 4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-acetic acid to alcohol followed by cyclisation and dehydrogenation. But yields in the reduction of the ester of quinoline-3-acetic acid derivative with LAH were poor. Hence these quinoline-3-acetic acid derivatives were cyclised to corresponding quinoline-lactones (III) according to Raman⁴. IR spectra (Nujol) of these lactone derivatives showed characteristic lactonyl carbonyl bands at 1830 cm^{-1} .

It was also thought of interest to prepare lactones having 6-membered ring by introducing one more methylene group. To prepare this, ethylbromo propionate was condensed with sodium salt of acetoacetanilide. α -Carboethoxyethylacetoacetanilide (IV) was obtained and was cyclised with conc. sulphuric acid to 4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-propionic acid (V). Cyclisation of (V) to a lactone of 4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-propionic acid with acetic anhydride or acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate or polyphosphoric acid was unsuccessful. An attempt was made to cyclise this acid by first converting it to acid chloride by treatment with thionyl chloride followed by cyclisation in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride using benzene as solvent, but surprisingly a propiophenone derivative (VI) was obtained. Its IR spectrum (Nujol) showed a characteristic ketonic carbonyl band at 1680 cm^{-1} .

EXPERIMENTAL

IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 237 grating spectrophotometer.

5-Methyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano(3,2-c)quinoline : A mixture of 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 ml.) and triethylamine (4 ml.) was heated in an oil bath at 110° for 16 hr. It was then poured in ice cold water and the product which separated crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 1), m.p. 180°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 73.77; H, 4.18; N, 6.50%. $C_{13}H_9O_2N$ requires C, 73.93; H, 4.26; N, 6.63%).

5-Methyl-3-phenyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano(3,2-c)quinoline : A mixture of 2-methyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 ml.), triethylamine (4 ml.) and phenylacetic acid (1 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 110° for 16 hrs. It was worked up as above. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 204°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 78.97; H, 4.45; N, 4.81%. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2N$ requires C, 79.43; H, 4.52; N, 4.87%).

IR spectrum : 1735 cm^{-1} (lactonyl carbonyl band).

5,7-Dimethyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano(3,2-c)quinoline : A mixture of 2,8-dimethyl-3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 ml.) and triethylamine (4 ml.) was refluxed as above. The product crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 170°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 74.62; H, 5.08; N, 5.99%. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 74.66; H, 4.88; N, 6.22%).

IR spectrum : 1740 cm^{-1} (lactonyl carbonyl band).

5,7-Dimethyl-3-phenyl-2-oxo-2H-pyrano(3,2-c)quinoline : The 3-phenyl derivative was obtained when the reaction was carried out with phenyl acetic acid (1 g.) and 2,8-dimethyl-3-methyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (1 g.) as described above. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 178°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 79.63; H, 4.96; N, 4.46%. $C_{20}H_{15}O_2$ requires C, 79.71; H, 4.98; N, 4.65%).

IR spectrum : 1725 cm^{-1} (lactonyl carbonylband).

Quinolino-lactones

General procedures : Condensation of sodium salt of acetoacetarylamides with ethyl-bromoacetate : α -Carboethoxymethylacetoacetarylamide : Acetoacetarylamide (0.03 m) in dry benzene (70 ml.) was refluxed with pulverised sodium (0.03 ml.) for 5 hr. and cooled to room temperature. Ethyl bromoacetate (0.03 ml.) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed further for 4 hr. It was cooled and diluted with water. The two layers were separated and aqueous layer was extracted with benzene. The combined benzene extracts were washed with water and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. Benzene was distilled out and the residue was purified by passing over alumina in benzene. The product (Table 1) crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 1). Yield 4.5 g.

TABLE 1

Condensation of sodium salt acetoacetarylamide with ethyl bromoacetate

No.	α -Carboethoxymethyl acetoacet-	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis%					
				Reqd.			Found		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	<i>o</i> -Toluidide	82	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	64.98	6.86	5.05	64.89	6.71	5.14
2.	<i>m</i> -Xylidide	126	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	65.97	7.21	4.81	65.84	7.10	4.40
3.	α -Naphthylamide	130	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	69.63	6.07	4.47	68.89	6.21	4.07
4.	<i>p</i> -Xylidide	Thick oil was obtained							
5.	<i>p</i> -Toluidide	Thick oil was obtained.							

Cyclisation of α -Carboethoxymethylacetoacetarylamide : 4-Methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-acetic acid derivatives : The above derivative (2 g.) was treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (5 ml.) and left overnight. It was heated on a water bath for 45 mins. The reaction mixture was added to water and the product (Table 2) which separated crystallised from glacial acetic acid. Yield 1.4 g.

Lactone of 4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-acetic acid derivatives : The above acid (1 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (3 ml.) in an oil bath at 100° for 4 hr. The cooled mixture was diluted with ice water and stirred well. The separated product was filtered and washed with water. The product was stirred with sodium bicarbonate solution and the insoluble solid (Table 3) crystallised from dilute acetone. Yield 0.4 g.

TABLE 2

4-Methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-acetic acid derivatives

No.	Substituent in 4-methyl-2- hydroxyquinoline 3-acetic acid	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis%					
				Reqd.			Found		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	8-methyl	295	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	67.53	5.62	6.06	67.43	5.50	5.95
2.	6,8-dimethyl	308	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	68.57	6.12	5.17	68.36	5.96	5.55
3.	7,8-benzo-	308	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ N	71.91	4.86	5.24	71.68	4.97	4.92
4.	5,8-dimethyl	278	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	68.57	6.12	5.17	68.53	6.04	5.37
5.	6-methyl	305	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	67.53	5.62	6.06	67.98	6.00	6.43

TABLE 3

Lactones of 4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-acetic acid derivatives

No.	Substituent in lactone of 4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-acetic acid	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis%					
				Reqd.		Found			
				C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	8-methyl	199	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	73.23	5.16	6.57	72.86	5.01	6.12
2.	6,8-dimethyl	268	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	74.00	5.72	6.16	74.43	5.96	6.30
3.	7,8-benzo	256	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	77.73	4.45	5.66	77.63	4.37	5.36
4.	5,8-dimethyl	238	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	74.00	5.72	6.16	73.64	5.64	6.46
5.	6-methyl	230	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	73.23	5.16	6.57	73.45	5.12	6.10

Condensation of sodium salt of acetoacetanilide with ethyl-bromopropionate and its cyclisation to 4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-propionic acid : Acetoacetanilide (5.1 g.) in dry benzene (50 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath with pulverised sodium (0.7 g.) for 6 hr. To the cooled solution was added ethyl bromopropionate (5.4 ml.) and the reaction mixture was refluxed further for 5 hr. It was added to water. The two layers formed were separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with benzene. The combined benzene extracts were dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. On removal of benzene the product separated in liquid form.

The above oily product was treated with conc. sulphuric acid (10 ml.) and left overnight. It was then heated on a water bath for 1 hr. and poured over ice water. The product which separated crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 237°. Yield 3 g. (Found : C, 68.82; H, 5.58; N, 6.30. C₁₃H₁₃O₃N requires C, 68.43; H, 5.70; N, 6.14%).

Attempted cyclisation : The above acid (1 g.) when treated with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and fused sodium acetate or polyphosphoric acid at 120° for 3 hr. and the reaction mixture poured over water, the product which separated was found to be original acid.

(4-Methyl-2-hydroxy-3-quinolyl)ethylphenyl ketone : 4-Methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-propionic acid (1 g.) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (5 ml.) and on a water bath for 4 hr. After removing excess of thionyl chloride dry benzene, and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) was slowly added and heating continued for further 2 hr. Benzene was removed and the mixture was poured over ice water and hydrochloric acid (3 ml.). The product crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 237°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found : C, 78.58; H, 5.57; N, 4.98. $C_{18}H_{17}NO_2$ requires C, 78.34; H, 5.84; N, 4.81%).

4,6-Dimethyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-propionic acid : Acetoacet-*p*-toluidide (3.8 g.) in dry benzene (40 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath with pulverised sodium (0.5 g.) for 5 hr. Ethyl bromopropionate (3.6 g.) was added and refluxed further for 5 hr. On working up as before α -Carboethoxyethylacetoacet-*p*-toluidide separated as thick oil. This was cyclised with conc. sulphuric acid (8 ml.). On working up as before the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 252°. Yield 2 g. (Found : C, 68.68; H, 6.32; N, 6.00. $C_{14}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 68.56; H, 6.12; N, 5.71%).

*α -Carboethoxyethyl acetoacet-*o*-toluidide* : Acetoacet-*o*-toluidide (3.8 g.) in dry benzene (40 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath with pulverised sodium (0.5 g.) for 4 hr. Ethyl bromopropionate (3.6 g.) was then added and the reaction mixture was refluxed further for 5 hr. On working up as before the product crystallised from ether petroleum, m.p. 85°. Yield 3 g. (Found: C, 65.58; H, 6.97; N, 5.04. $C_{16}H_{21}O_4N$ requires C, 65.98; N, 7.21; N, 4.81%).

4,8-Dimethyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-propionic acid : The above compound (3 g.) was cyclised with conc. sulphuric acid (6 ml.) as described above. On working up as before the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 244°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 68.89; H, 6.21; N, 5.40. $C_{14}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 68.56; H, 6.12; N, 5.71%).

(4,6-Dimethyl-2-hydroxy-3-quinolyl)ethylphenylketone : This was prepared from 4,6-dimethyl-2-hydroxyquinoline-3-propionic acid by reacting it with thionyl chloride followed by anhydrous aluminium chloride in dry benzene. On working up as before the product crystallised from benzene, m.p. 178°. (Found : C, 78.61; H, 6.32; N, 5.02. $C_{20}H_{19}O_2N$ requires C, 78.69; H, 6.23; N, 5.59%).

Thanks are due to Prof. E. Gellert, Wollongong University College, Wollongong, N.S.W. Australia for IR Spectra, Prof. S. Sethna for keen interest in the work and Dr. S. S. Lele for microanalysis.

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